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Technological Advancement and Public Administration: Challenges Faced by the Myanmar Port
Authority

Master thesis written under supervision of
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Declaration

I, Aung Khant Min, a student of University of Wroclaw pursuing a master's degree in administration of International Organizations, hereby declare that the master's thesis title " Technological Advancement and Public Administration: Challenges Faced by the Myanmar Port Authority" is an original and independent work of research undertaken by me under the supervision of Dr hab. Barbara Kowalczyk of the University of Wroclaw.

I further declare that this thesis has not been submitted, either in part or in full, for the award of any degree or diploma at this or any other university or institution of higher learning.

Date: 20th June 2025

Place: Wroclaw

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Public Administration as an area of Government

Public Administration is the completing the task of the government policies by planning, organization, directing, controlling and coordinating in order to control the operation of the government.¹ There are various form of definition as it was historically difficult to explain such as “ *Public Administration... is the action part of government, the means by which the purposes and goals of government are realized.*”², moreover the other one mentioned related with political stated as; “*Public administration as a field is mainly concerned with the means for implementing political values.*”, furthermore some express regarding public setting that involves all branches of government, plays a crucial role in public policy formation, differs significantly from private administration, and is interconnected with various private entities and individuals; “*Public Administration (a) is a cooperative group effort in a public setting; (b) covers all three branches-executive, legislative, and judicial – and their interrelationships; (c) has the important role in the formation of public policy, is thus part of the political process*”³.

Implementing government policies and managing public programs and services are the main focusses of the diverse area of public administration. The creation and implementation of public policy, the administration of public sector institutions, and the delivery of services to residents are just a few of the many activities it includes. In order for the government to operate effectively and for public goods and services to be delivered, it is essential. Especially, public sectors area in Port Authority which is tremendously bustling workplace interpret as the excessive requirement of good governance and administration in the area of governmental management in Myanmar.

¹ Mosher, F. C. , Page, . Edward C. and Chapman, . Brian (2024, July 18). public administration. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/public-administration>

² Britannica, s.v. “Public Administration: The Soviet Union,” accessed December 17, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/public-administration/The-Soviet-Union>.

³ Eastern Kentucky University Online. (n.d.). *The relationship between public administration and politics*. Retrieved from <https://ekuonline.eku.edu/blog/public-administration/the-relationship-between-public-administration-and-politics>

1.2. Importance and its process of the Port Authority in Myanmar

Figure 1: Myanma Port Authority Main office ⁴

The role of the Port Authorities plays a critical role for the whole economic sector of Myanmar with strategically located between South Asia, Southeast Asia, and China, along with connectivity to the strongest and fastest-growing economic countries⁵. A single impact from the authorities of Myanmar may affect not only the volume of the trade but also other sectors, including its social-economic growth, the investment from foreign as well as local-foreign partnerships, strategic positioning within regional logistics, and the connection of the trade. Myanma Port Authority, which was established under the Ministry of Transport and

⁴ Myanmar Port Authority (n.d.) *About*. Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/about/> (Accessed: 1 May 2025)

⁵ World Bank (2022) *Why ports matter for the global economy*. Available at: <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/transport/why-ports-matter-global-economy> (Accessed: 2 April 2025).

Communications, is the major operational hub for major ports around the country of Myanmar, including the Port of Yangon, the famous and most developed so-called Thailawa Port and as well as numerous inland waterways. Moreover, it operates and handles the whole country’s export and import activities, ensuring that all the ports are equipped with modern infrastructure. Furthermore, it handles the smooth trading in cargo and traffic of passengers, which contributes to the efficiency of Myanmar’s trade networks. Conditionally, among all government offices around Myanmar, MPA is one of the busiest and exhausted workplaces as it is particularly significant given the geographical location of Myanmar as a connective hub between Southeast Asia, South Asia, and maritime routes of trade for global trade.

Figure 2: Organization Chart and Ports Operation by MPA⁶

According to the figure (2), the responsible and accountable person at the top level of the Port Authority in Myanmar is shown as the Managing Director and General Manager, which is the major decision-making level for every port and department of the whole country. Established with nine departments, including Traffic, shipping agency, marine, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, account, personnel, store, and IR & HRD department, as well as consisting of two divisions and four ports, which are the medical and internal audit divisions and Rakhine,

⁶ Myanmar Port Authority (n.d.) *About*. Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/about/> (Accessed: 1May 2025)

Ayeyarwady, Mon, and Tanintharyi regional ports. According to the chart, the general manager holds the highest level of decision-making power and authority for the port of Ayeyarwady region.

The most significant responsibilities of MPAs lie in well-ordered regulating maritime activities and enforcing compliance with international standards. In addition, licences issuing, shipping permits and operations related to ports, establish and control, ensuring with safety protocols, rules and regulations as well as environmental cases in surrounding sites and the surrounding area of its⁷. Moreover, to maintain the necessary security and safety of the port facilities, the organisation complies with the International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code. To add to it plays an important role in the outlook for the operation in trade, the infrastructure of the port is appropriately maintained as well as well-equipped to handle the rising volumes of trade.

They tightly communicate and negotiate with local and global stakeholders by completing, improving and precaution activities regarding with efficiency, management of port and on-site operation. Furthermore, sustainable in environment plays vital role for MPA in order to reduce any types of pollution, waste-management and preserve ecosystem for the marine environment by law and regulations enforcement which involves authoritarian monitoring the vessels from emissions, regulating ballast water discharge and make sure to follow the protection of environmental laws from various activity from port⁸. In addition to its regulatory functions, MPA actively collaborates with global maritime organizations, such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO), to adopt and implement international maritime safety and security measures⁹.

⁷ Myanmar Port Authority (MPA), 2024. *About Us*. [online] Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/about/> [Accessed 13 May 2025].

⁸ International Maritime Organization (IMO), 2023. *International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code*. [online] Available at: <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Security/Pages/ISPSCode.aspx> [Accessed 2nd feb 2025]

⁹ International Maritime Organization (IMO), 2023. *International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code*. [online] Available at: <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Security/Pages/ISPSCode.aspx> [Accessed 1st Jan 2025]

1.3. The Challenges faced in Port Authorities regarding public administration

The main important role for the national economy, which is run by Myanmar port authority among other authorities, is to smooth trade and serve as a gateway for exports and imports. Nonetheless, the administration and the system face various significant challenges, including the scope of power, inefficient governance actions, a lack of physical and educational infrastructure, Taxation difficulties, and environmental care issues. To be efficient and enhance their contribution to the local and international trade sector, there are several vital areas for improvement. Therefore, this section will explore the specifics of these challenges along with actual evidence and research, as well as secondary data, along with academic insights.

1.3.1. Lack of governance and institutional inefficiencies

The basic challenges facing Myanmar's Port Authorities are that there is a lack of government inefficiency in both governance and coordination operations in all institutions. There are lots of The administration of ports is often fragmented, with overlapping roles among various government bodies such as the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA), customs departments, and other regulatory agencies. These redundancies lead to delays in decision-making and create confusion among stakeholders. Studies highlight that centralized decision-making processes in Myanmar have historically limited the ability of port authorities to respond effectively to local and international needs¹⁰.

Corruption is another significant issue as Myanmar was ranked 157th out of 180 countries on Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index in 2021, reflecting widespread governance challenges, including within port operations¹¹. Complex customs procedures and unclear fee structures create opportunities for rent-seeking behavior, further eroding investor confidence¹².

¹⁰ Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2018. *Myanmar Transport Sector Policy Note: Ports and Logistics*. [online] Manila: ADB. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/456206/myanmar-transport-policy-note-ports-logistics.pdf> [Accessed 23rd Jan 2025]

¹¹ Transparency International, 2021. *Corruption Perceptions Index 2021*. [online] Available at: <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2021/index/mmr> [Accessed 25th Feb 2025].

¹² World Bank, 2021. *Myanmar Economic Monitor: Coping with COVID-19*. [online] Washington, DC: World Bank. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/myanmar/overview> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

1.3.2. Infrastructure Shortcomings and Technology Shortfalls

These are the significant issues regarding infrastructure that can limit the process and efficiency of Myanmar's ports, as well as struggles with antiquated handling in cargo places and container storage insufficiency. Furthermore, because of its shallow depth, larger ships cannot access it, forcing many to rely on smaller feeder vessels, which drives up costs and reduces competitiveness. Furthermore, poor rail and road links between the ports and interior regions complicate logistics even more and prolong turnaround times¹³.

Moreover, technology deficits are also the main issues after infrastructure compared to other modern ports in neighboring countries such as Singapore, Thailand, and Malaysia, as most operations are made by the Myanmar port authority, which still depends on manual techniques for handling the cargo, tracking, and customs procedures. It's all because we are relying on outdated systems, which are inherently inefficient and significantly increase the risk of errors and delays. Myanmar has fallen well behind much of the international community in developing digital port management technology that a new report from the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific says is now standard around the world¹⁴. To that end, to remove such roadblocks, investments in digital solutions and infrastructure upgrades are critical¹⁵.

1.3.3. Regulatory and Policy Difficulties

Among all the challenges, the ability to attract the global shipping lines and FDI (foreign direct investments) is the most challenging factor for Myanmar because of its outdated and old administration of Port regulations. For instance, the 1954-enacted Myanmar Port Authority Law has not been sufficiently revised to take into account contemporary maritime standards and demands of global trade. Long and bureaucratic licensing procedures further complicate the

¹³ Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2018. *Myanmar Transport Sector Policy Note: Ports*. [online] Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/452781/myanmar-transport-note-ports.pdf> [Accessed 21st April 2025].

¹⁴ United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (UNESCAP), 2023. *Digital and Sustainable Trade Facilitation in Asia and the Pacific*. [online] Available at: <https://www.unescap.org/> [Accessed 4th Feb 2025].

¹⁵ Transparency International, 2021. *Corruption Perceptions Index 2021*. [online] Available at: [Transparency International CPI 2021 – Myanmar](https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2021/myanmar) [Accessed 13 March 2025].

regulatory environment and deter private sector involvement in port development and management.¹⁶

Another problem is that port-related policies are inconsistent and opaque. For example, tariffs and fees are frequently subject to change without sufficient notice, which causes uncertainty for shipping lines and businesses. Aligning Myanmar's port regulations with international standards, such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO) guidelines, would enhance investor confidence and enable the country's ports to compete more effectively on a global scale¹⁷.

1.3.4. Human Resource Limitations

The shortage of competent employees in Myanmar Port Authority is an additional significant problem. Many officer especially from the top level management sectors, lack in knowledge of advance port management techniques, including sustainable development, advance or simple computerized systems, and AI applied logistics. Institutional efficiency is further weakened by high staff turnover due to low payment and limited opportunities for career advancement in the public sector, as well as the civil disobedience movement that occurred in 2021 due to the military coup and death from the conflict. A report from the Myanmar Maritime University (2021) states that the need for specialized training programs to enhance the capacity of port workers and administrators is rising¹⁸. Operational inefficiencies in Myanmar's ports will persist without adequate human resource development.

1.3.5. Social and Environmental Issues

Myanmar's port activities have significant environmental and social impacts that are still unresolved or carefully controlled is inadequately addressed. Degradation of coastal ecosystems is caused by ship pollution, weak waste management, and lax environmental regulations. Mangrove

¹⁶ **Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2022.** *Myanmar Transport Sector Assessment, Strategy, and Road Map*. [online] ADB.

Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/linked-documents/mya-50381-006-ssa.pdf> [Accessed 11st March 2025].

¹⁷ **International Maritime Organization (IMO), 2023.** *List of IMO Conventions*. [online] IMO. Available at: <https://www.imo.org/en/about/Conventions/Pages/ListOfConventions.aspx> [Accessed 13 May 2025]

¹⁸ **Myanmar Maritime University (MMU), 2021.** *Home Page*. [online] MMU. Available at: <https://www.mmu.edu.mm/News.aspx?NewsID=264> [Accessed 13 May 2025].

forests, for instance, are vital in preventing erosion and sustaining biodiversity along the coast, and their destruction has sparked worries about Thilawa Port's expansion¹⁹.

There are also many social issues, like local communities being uprooted. Residents have been displaced as a result of large-scale port projects, like the Kyaukphyu Deep Sea Port, frequently without proper compensation or relocation plans²⁰. Concerns regarding the long-term viability of port development projects have been raised by these problems, which have also caused opposition from impacted communities²¹. These issues can be lessened by enacting stricter environmental laws and embracing inclusive development strategies.

1.4. Research Objectives and Aim

1.4.1. Aims

The main goal of this research is to develop Myanmar's port system and modern technology to guarantee simple, effective, and well-organized systematic port operations procedures. To meet international standards, this entails recognising current issues and dilemmas, suggesting innovative advance technological solutions, and encouraging sustainable development and implementation within the port system.

Objectives of this research

1. Assess the Present Status of Myanmar's Port Systems

¹⁹ World Wildlife Fund (WWF), 2023. *New hope for Myanmar's mangrove forests*. [online] WWF Updates. Available at: <https://updates.panda.org/new-hope-for-myanmars-mangrove-forests> [Accessed 18 March 2025]. (Compare to) Mangrove Alliance, 2021. *The State of the World's Mangroves 2021*. [online] Available at: <https://www.mangrovealliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/The-State-of-the-Worlds-Mangroves-2021-FINAL.pdf> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

²⁰ Business & Human Rights Resource Centre, 2023. *Myanmar: Impact assessment consultation for port projects takes place in Kyaukphyu, Rakhine State*. [online] Available at: <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/latest-news/myanmar-impact-assessment-consultation-for-port-projects-takes-place-in-kyaukphyu-rakhine-state/> [Accessed 13 May 2025]. (Compare to) International Commission of Jurists (ICJ), 2016. *Myanmar: It's time for transparency over the Kyaukphyu Special Economic Zone*. [online] ICJ. Available at: <https://www.icj.org/resource/myanmar-its-time-for-transparency-over-the-kyaukphyu-special-economic-zone/> [Accessed 6th April 2025]

²¹ Lowy Institute, 2023. *Why is Myanmar's new deep-sea port such hot property?* [online] The Interpreter. Available at: <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/why-myanmar-s-new-deep-sea-port-such-hot-property> [Accessed 1st Jan 2025]. (Compare to) The Defense Post, 2025. *Aid Group Says 4,000 Displaced by Battle for Key Myanmar Port Site*. [online] Available at: <https://thedefensepost.com/2025/03/06/fighting-myanmar-port-site-displaced/> [Accessed 1st Jan 2025].

- Research regarding the current use of technology, its infrastructure, and operational procedures currently run in Myanmar's ports.
 - Defined the current system's bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and deficiencies.
2. Suggest Improvements in Technology
 - Suggest appropriate technologies that can able to enhance port operations without any delay and issues, as an example of automation, digitisation, and data analytics.
 - Explain how blockchain, IoT, and simple AI might be used to streamline port systems and operations
 3. Pushly supports Systematic and Long-term Sustainable Port Development
 - Suggest ways to bring Myanmar's port system into compliance with global operational and environmental standards.
 - Promote methodical techniques to guarantee efficient and reliable cargo and documentation processing.
 4. Enhance Competitiveness in the Economy
 - Explain how modernisation can sharply increase Myanmar's ability to compete in both local and international markets.
 - To entice investments in port infrastructure, suggest policies and incentives.

1.5. Key Research Questions

1. What are the current issues to Myanmar's port system's adoption of contemporary technologies?
This question raises some issues, such as antiquated and outdated infrastructure, a lack of technical know-how, or legal restrictions or weakness.
2. How can technological developments enhance productivity and lessen bottlenecks in port operations for the country's GDP?
This examines particular technological solutions and how they might affect operational procedures.
3. What best solutions from around the world can be used to develop Myanmar's port infrastructure?
This looks like some research information on international standards and procedures that are pertinent to Myanmar's situation.

4. How can AI automation and digitisation develop Myanmar's ports' organised processing?
This focuses on specific technological areas like automated cargo handling, e-documentation, and data analytics.

Critical questions to address

1. Advancement needs of Technological in Port Administration
 - What are the key Myanmar port system's most immediate and essential technological needs and deficits in this era?
 - Which advanced technologies, like blockchain, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things, are best suited for use in Myanmar's ports, balance with the knowledge of its employees?

1.6. Significance of the Study

There are several reasons why it's vital to look into modernising Myanmar's port system, notably to make the country's administrative, technological, and economic systems better:

1. Being able to compete in trade and build the economy

Myanmar's ports are very important to the country's economy because they make it easier for goods to come in and out of the country. The study will look at how new technologies can make them work better. Streamlined operations will make Myanmar more competitive in both regional and international markets, cut trade costs, and bring in more foreign shipping lines.

2. Changes to policies and government

The research will assist make policymaking better by finding old rules and bad governance that don't work. Regulatory reform suggestions will help port management systems that are clear, work well, and are well-coordinated, and that follow international marine standards.

3. Updating technology and infrastructure

The project will use new technologies, such as automation (vehicles, cranes, etc), digitisation from documentation, and data analytics to come up with ideas for how to update Myanmar's port infrastructure. These changes will make it easier to alter the cargo without human power, get rid of things that do not need, and make the whole operation more efficient.

4. Growth That Will Last

The main goal of this study is to look at how to grow ports in a way that is good for the environment and society. Recommendations for environmental compliance and best practices will assist Myanmar in reaching its long-term development goals and safeguarding its coastal habitats.

1.6.1. Scope of the Study

- **Geographic Focus:** In addition to inland waterways, the study focusses on Myanmar's main ports, especially the Port of Yangon and Thilawa Port.
- **Topic Coverage:** It looks at governance issues, infrastructure deficiencies, workforce development needs, and the state of port operations today.
- **Technological Insights:** To enhance port operations, the study investigates the use of cutting-edge technologies like automation, digitisation, blockchain, and artificial intelligence.
- **Comparative Analysis:** The study examines international best practices and evaluates how well they apply to the Myanmar context.

1.6.2. Limitations of the Study

The study has several limitations that should be noted, despite providing insightful information on the interaction between technology and public administration in Myanmar's port industry. The lack of accurate and current data on port operations and administrative duties is a significant obstacle. It is challenging to perform in-depth or comparative analyses due to the lack of transparency and consistent record access. Furthermore, Myanmar's ongoing political and economic instability, particularly since the military takeover in 2021, may impact not only the implementation of suggested reforms but also the responsiveness of relevant institutions, which could diminish the practical significance of this study.

Additionally, one of the biggest obstacles to digital transformation in the port industry is still technological limitations. The high cost of modern technologies and a lack of technical expertise can delay or impede adoption in many of Myanmar's ports, which still rely heavily on antiquated infrastructure and manual procedures. The study also points out that because Myanmar's port systems are in a far different stage of development than those of more developed nations like Singapore or Malaysia, its conclusions may not be as broadly applicable as they could be. Finally, although administrative and technological issues are the main focus of the research, environmental and social issues like community displacement are only touched upon in passing and should be the subject of more thorough, focused investigation in subsequent studies.

Chapter 2: Literature Review & Conceptual Framework

2.1 Public Administration and Technology

In Myanmar, the topic of this relation between public administration and technology is the serious matter which most of the employees in the sector of public could be against this as traditionally administration running in the public sectors are tightly associated with bureaucratic structure and full loads of paper-work as well as variety of steps and procedures to generate a proper decision that tends to be tremendously resist on changing as they might lose some benefits which are limited in the outer world with advance technology. Nevertheless, a significant rise in information and communication technology, such as social media and media streaming, has led to the transformation of the entire world's administrative structure, and also affects public administration in Myanmar. The role of technology has enormously driven the force of decision-making procedures, operational management, and service delivery. The increasing impact of digital tools in public sector reform is highlighted by academics like Heeks (2006)²² and Fountain (2001)²³, who concentrate on responsiveness, efficiency, and transparency.

Technology's role in public administration is both a promise and a challenge in developing nations like Myanmar. On the one hand, digital systems provide resources for effective data management, accountability, and service delivery²⁴. However, a digital divide in implementation is created by a lack of digital skills, inadequate infrastructure, and resistance to change. Technology is essential for improving cargo tracking, customs clearance, trade facilitation, and stakeholder coordination in ports and transport logistics. Technology development is vital for organisations like the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA), a significant government agency in charge of the nation's maritime infrastructure, to comply with international standards and facilitate more efficient logistics operations. However, progress is still hindered by institutional flaws, outdated systems, and inadequate digital governance.

²² Heeks, R., 2006. *Implementing and managing eGovernment: An international text*. London: SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://sk.sagepub.com/book/implementing-and-managing-egovernment> [Accessed 12 May 2025].

²³ Fountain, J.E., 2001. *Building the virtual state: Information technology and institutional change*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution Press. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7864/j.ctvc59n3> [Accessed 13 May 2025].

²⁴ Than, H.T., 2021. *Port Governance Structure: The Port of Yangon*. [pdf] ResearchGate. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354444411_Port_Governance_Structure_the_Port_of_Yangon [Accessed 13 May 2025].

2.2 Advancement of technology in Public administration/ evolution of E-government

Early e-government efforts, from the late 1990s to the early 2000s, concentrated on digitizing already existing services, like posting policy documents and forms online. There was little opportunity for interaction during this mostly static phase. A move towards service-oriented governance was signaled by the introduction of more interactive features by governments by the middle of the 2000s, such as online applications, e-tax filing, and feedback mechanisms. The idea of digital governance surfaced as the field developed. Beyond simple online services, digital governance encompasses the strategic application of data, automation, artificial intelligence (AI), and real-time systems to promote responsiveness, transparency, and evidence-based decision-making. It seeks to restructure government procedures to be more inclusive, data-driven, and focused on the needs of the people.

In the public sector, digital transformation involves integrating digital technology into every aspect of government operations, with a significant impact on operational effectiveness and service delivery. Digital transformation, according to the OECD (2019), involves more than just implementing new technology; it also entails rethinking public services and procedures to be agile, data-driven, and citizen-centric.²⁵

G2G (Government to Government), G2B (Government to Business), and G2C (Government to Citizen) frameworks are examples of e-governance models that illustrate how public agencies communicate digitally with internal departments, businesses, and the public at large²⁶. Single window systems and port community systems (PCS) have emerged as global standards for digital integration in port administration, facilitating smooth collaboration between various stakeholders, including shipping companies, terminal operators, and customers²⁷.

In developed countries that provide nearly all public services online, such as South Korea, Denmark, and Estonia, digital governance has advanced quickly. The advantages of these nations

²⁵ **OECD**, 2019. *The Path to Becoming a Data-Driven Public Sector*. [online] Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/gov/the-path-to-becoming-a-data-driven-public-sector-059814a7-en.htm> [Accessed 1st March 2024].

²⁶ **United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA)**, 2022. *UN E-Government Survey 2022: The Future of Digital Government*. [online] Available at: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Reports/UN-E-Government-Survey-2022> [Accessed 2nd March 2024].

²⁷ **World Bank**, 2021. *Digital Port Community Systems: Lessons from Global Implementation*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/transport/publication/digital-port-community-systems> [Accessed 1st March 2024].

include strong digital infrastructure, extensive internet usage, supportive legal systems, and high digital literacy levels among their populations.

Consequently, services like digital ID systems, automated welfare delivery, online licensing, and e-tax filing are widely accepted and trusted²⁸. However, many barriers hinder successful digital transformation in Myanmar and other developing countries. These obstacles include low digital literacy among civil servants, limited internet access in rural areas, bureaucratic resistance to change, and insufficient ICT infrastructure.

A lack of reliable funding and political uncertainty also complicates ongoing digital governance reforms²⁹. Bwalya et al. (2014) concentrate on African and Asian contexts, emphasising that political will, legal reform, training, and public involvement are all necessary for effective e-governance³⁰. They emphasise that a lot of digital government projects fail because of institutional and sociopolitical issues rather than technical ones.

In conclusion, even though digital transformation has enormous potential to enhance governance, its effectiveness varies greatly based on the institutional preparedness, cultural acceptance, and level of development of the nation. Coordination of policy, infrastructure, and human capital reform is necessary in nations like Myanmar to bridge the gap between aspirations and realities.³¹

2.3. Applications of AI in Port Operations

AI is used in customs and border control to automate risk assessment by identifying potentially illegal or high-risk shipments through the analysis of large datasets. This preserves security

²⁸ OECD, 2023. *2023 OECD Digital Government Index*. [online] OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2023-oecd-digital-government-index_1a89ed5e-en.html [Accessed 20 May 2025]. (Compare to) United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), 2022. *UN E-Government Survey 2022: The Future of Digital Government*. [online] Available at: <https://desapublications.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/2022-09/Web%20version%20E-Government%202022.pdf> [Accessed 20 May 2025].

²⁹ World Bank, 2025. *Digital Transformation Overview: Development news, research, data*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/digital/overview> [Accessed 20 Feb 2024]. (Compare to) International Trade Administration, 2024. *Burma - Digital Economy*. [online] Available at: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/burma-digital-economy> [Accessed 20 Feb 2024].

³⁰ Bwalya, K.J., & Mutula, S.M., 2014. *E-Government: Implementation, Adoption and Synthesis in Developing Countries*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG

³¹ Hanna, N.K., 2009. *E-Government for Good Governance in Developing Countries: Empirical Evidence from the e-Government Projects in India*. [online] United Nations Asian and Pacific Training Centre for Information and Communication Technology for Development (UN-APCICT). Available at: https://www.unapcict.org/sites/default/files/2019-01/821.%20IDL-52671_0.pdf [Accessed 20 Feb 2024] compare to Arthur D. Little, 2017. *Digital Transformation in Developing Countries*. [online] Available at: <https://www.adlittle.com/it-en/insights/viewpoints/digital-transformation-developing-countries> [Accessed 20 Feb 2024]

standards while enabling quicker clearance times. AI-powered solutions aid in cargo management and logistics by predicting equipment maintenance requirements, tracking inventory flow, and optimizing container placement³². AI-driven sensors and machine vision, which track vehicle movement and ease congestion, also improve traffic monitoring at ports.

One of the most important aspects of the public sector's digital transformation is the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into port operations. Ports must handle growing cargo volumes while enhancing operational effectiveness, safety, and regulatory compliance as global trade heats up. The way port authorities and customs agencies operate is being completely transformed by AI technologies, such as machine learning, computer vision, and real-time analytics.

2.3.1. Handling Cargo

Robotic sorting, automated cranes, and intelligent storage systems are all made possible by AI, which improves cargo handling. These systems minimize human error, speed up loading and unloading, and optimize container placement using real-time data and algorithms. AI-assisted cranes, for instance, are used in ports in Rotterdam and Singapore to speed up turnaround times and lower operating expenses³³.

2.3.2. Clearance of Customs

AI speeds up and improves the detection of illegal or high-risk shipments in customs operations by automating risk assessment and cargo profiling. To identify irregularities, AI systems examine trade trends, scanned documents, and historical data. This improves border security in addition to expediting customs clearance³⁴.

2.3.3. Traffic Surveillance

Within ports, ship and vehicle traffic is tracked using computer vision and AI-powered sensors. These systems minimise delays, optimise dock scheduling, and control congestion. To improve

³² iCustoms, 2024. *How AI is Modernising Customs Processes*. [online] Available at: <https://www.icustoms.ai/blogs/how-ai-modernises-customs-processes/> [Accessed 23 January 2025].

³³ Dinh, Q., 2024. *Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to Enhance Port Operation Efficiency*. Polish Maritime Research, 2(2024), pp.140-155. Available at: https://yadda.icm.edu.pl/baztech/element/bwmeta1.element/baztech-d3c36e5d-55d6-4f53-afc3-60ed347fe263/c/15_PMRes_Dinh_140_155.pdf [Accessed 20 May 2025].

³⁴ iCustoms, 2024. *How AI is Modernising Customs Processes*. [online] Available at: <https://www.icustoms.ai/blogs/how-ai-modernises-customs-processes/> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

port flow and safety, machine learning algorithms can predict traffic patterns and modify logistics accordingly³⁵.

2.3.4. Predictive Maintenance

Equipment failure causes major downtime and losses for ports. IoT sensors are used in real-time machinery performance monitoring as part of AI applications in predictive maintenance. By warning operators of possible issues before they become serious, these systems extend the life of equipment and lower repair expenses³⁶.

2.3.5. Port Community Systems (PCS) and Smart Ports

AI is also essential to Port Community Systems (PCS) and Smart Ports, which are digital platforms that help stakeholders like freight forwarders, shipping lines, customs, and terminal operators exchange data. These AI-powered platforms facilitate improved regulatory compliance, expedited documentation, and real-time coordination³⁷. PCS platforms facilitate smooth cargo status tracking across the supply chain and eliminate redundant data entry.

³⁵ Photonics Spectra, 2023. *Machine Vision with AI Assists Traffic Monitoring*. [online] Available at: https://www.photonics.com/Articles/Machine_Vision_with_AI_Assists_Traffic_Monitoring/a70106 [Accessed 1st May 2025].

³⁶ Intelegain, 2025. *How AI is Transforming Container Tracking & Logistics Industry*. [online] Available at: <https://www.intelegain.com/how-ai-is-transforming-container-tracking-logistics-industry/> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

³⁷ World Bank, 2021. *Digital Port Community Systems: Lessons from Global Implementation*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/transport/publication/digital-port-community-systems> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

Figure 3: Port Community system

All of the key players in the port logistics ecosystem are integrated digitally by the central node, the Port Community System in the figure 3, which includes:

- Government agencies: Harbour Master's Office, Customs, Port Authority, and Border Control;
- Service providers: General Port Services, Stevedores, and TowingShippers, forwarding agents, maritime agents, truckers, and warehouses are examples of private logistics actors.
- Specialised operations: Quantity and Safety Control, Dangerous Cargo Management

The PCS connects each of these stakeholders, allowing for:Data sharing in real time (cargo status, ship arrivals, inspection reports)

- Decreased duplication of documentation
- Better resource allocation, tracking, and scheduling

The United Nations Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business (UN/CEFACT) and the International Maritime Organisation have recommended PCS implementation as a way to modernise port governance and boost trade competitiveness, and this model is in line with their global standards³⁸.

³⁸ UN/CEFACT (2005) *Recommendation No. 33: Recommendation and Guidelines on Establishing a Single Window*. Geneva: United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. Available at: <https://unece.org/trade/uncefact/recommendations> (Accessed: 1st January 2025).

2.3.6. Advantages of Using AI

With its many benefits that improve productivity, decision-making, and worldwide competitiveness, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a potent instrument in contemporary port operations. The incorporation of AI-driven technologies is crucial for real-time coordination, resource optimisation, and enhanced service delivery as ports develop into intricate logistics hubs³⁹.

1. Efficiency in Operations

AI automates time-consuming and repetitive processes like scheduling, cargo classification, and document verification. This minimises operational delays and drastically cuts down on the workload for human employees. For instance, intelligent loading systems and AI-enabled cranes can streamline container handling procedures, increasing throughput and cutting dwell times⁴⁰.

2. Real-time tracking and visibility

Real-time cargo, vessel, and vehicle monitoring is made possible by AI-powered sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and data analytics platforms. These technologies improve responsiveness and planning accuracy by allowing port authorities to monitor container movements across terminals, identify irregularities, and respond immediately to disruptions⁴¹.

3. Predictive upkeep

AI assists port operators in preventing equipment failures before they happen. Artificial intelligence (AI) systems can forecast malfunctions and suggest preventative maintenance by continuously evaluating data from machinery (such as cranes, forklifts, and conveyor belts). This prolongs asset life cycles, lowers downtime, and avoids expensive malfunctions⁴².

4. Management of Traffic and Congestion

Ship and vehicle movement throughout the port area can be controlled by AI-powered computer vision systems and traffic sensors. Especially in crowded terminals like Yangon and Thilawa, these

³⁹ Kale Logistics Solutions, 2024. *The Key Role of AI, Automation, and Robotics in Port Efficiency*. Available at: <https://kalelogistics.com/usa/the-key-role-of-ai-automation-and-robotics-in-port-efficiency/> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

⁴⁰ Port Technology International, 2021. *How Can Ports Use Artificial Intelligence?*. Available at: <https://www.porttechnology.org/news/how-can-ports-use-artificial-intelligence/> [Accessed 1st January 2025].

⁴¹ Datahub Analytics, 2024. *Smart Ports: Optimizing Operations with AI and Automation*. Available at: <https://datahubanalytics.com/smart-ports-optimizing-operations-with-ai-and-automation/> [Accessed 21 May 2025].

⁴² Thetius, 2024. *The Role of AI in Port Management*. Available at: <https://thetius.com/the-role-of-ai-in-port-management/> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

tools aid in controlling gate operations, streamlining vessel berthing schedules, and easing traffic congestion⁴³.

5. Improvements to Security and Customs

AI improves customs clearance by automatically scanning cargo and risk profiles. By using past data and behaviour patterns to identify high-risk shipments, intelligent algorithms can expedite and improve the accuracy of inspections. This strikes a balance between the need for speed and the protection of national security and trade laws⁴⁴.

6. Anti-corruption and transparency

By digitally documenting each transaction, movement, and communication, AI increases port operations' transparency. Among stakeholders like shipping companies, exporters, and customs officers, this digital traceability increases trust and decreases opportunities for bribery or manipulation⁴⁵.

7. Environmental Management and Sustainability

AI technology can assist ports in increasing energy efficiency and lowering emissions. Smart systems, for example, can optimise fuel consumption, control lighting, and monitor pollution levels in real time, all of which are in line with sustainable port development objectives and international environmental standards⁴⁶.

⁴³ Business Insider, 2025. *A Massive Seaport in Texas Is Using an AI-Powered Digital Replica to Track Ships and Prepare for Emergencies*. Available at: <https://www.businessinsider.com/corpus-christi-port-ai-ship-tracking-emergency-training-2025-5> [Accessed 2nd May 2025].

⁴⁴ Kale Logistics Solutions, 2024. *The Key Role of AI, Automation, and Robotics in Port Efficiency*. Available at: <https://kalelogistics.com/usa/the-key-role-of-ai-automation-and-robotics-in-port-efficiency/> [Accessed 2nd May 2025].

⁴⁵ Hamburg Port Consulting, 2024. *AI-Powered Ports: Unlocking Efficiency, Sustainability, and Innovation*. Available at: <https://www.hamburgportconsulting.com/news/expert-insights/detail/ai-powered-ports-unlocking-efficiency-sustainability-and-innovation/> [Accessed 2nd May 2025].

⁴⁶ PierNext, 2023. *Will AI Take Over Port Management?*. Available at: <https://piernext.portdebarcelona.cat/en/technology/will-ai-take-over-port-management/> [Accessed 2nd May 2025].

2.4. Challenges in Implementing Technology in Public Institutions (PESTEL Analysis)

Although technological development has great potential to enhance public administration and service delivery, the case of Myanmar shows the great difficulties developing nations experience in properly implementing digital solutions within national institutions.

2.4.1. Political Instability (P)

The erratic political environment of Myanmar, especially after the military takeover in 2021, has seriously hampered efforts at digital governance. Long-term policy planning has been hampered by frequent leadership changes, the suspension of civilian control, and continuous civil unrest; institutional capacity to carry out technological reforms has also been undermined. Many government officials engaged in digital transformation projects have either left their positions because of the Civil Disobedience Movement (CDM) or have limited capacity to execute difficult modernisation projects under the current political uncertainty. As ADB (2022) notes, without political stability and institutional continuity, sustainable reform in sectors including port management and transportation is doubtful⁴⁷.

2.4.2. Infrastructure and the Digital Divide and economic instability (E)

Myanmar's infrastructure is severely lacking, especially outside of major cities. The unequal distribution of ICT infrastructure, power supplies, and internet access contributes to the ongoing digital divide between urban and rural populations as well as within government agencies. Only a small percentage of Myanmar's public institutions have consistent access to digital tools or systems, and many still use paper-based processes, according to the World Bank (2021)⁴⁸. This disparity hinders the successful implementation of digital governance programs and deters real-time decision-making and interagency data sharing.

Economically, a big obstacle is a small budget allotment. Due in part to sanctions and lower tax income, the limited resources of the Myanmar government mean that projects involving digital transformation in public infrastructure like ports are often given less priority than immediate

⁴⁷ ADB, 2021. *Myanmar and ADB*. [online] Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/where-we-work/myanmar> [Accessed 21 May 2025]

⁴⁸ World Bank, 2021. *Digital Development Partnership: Myanmar Country Profile*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/digitaldevelopment/publication/digital-development-partnership-country-profiles> [Accessed 21 May 2025].

operational needs. Usually dependent on foreign funding or donor support, large-scale investments in digital port management systems, artificial intelligence, or customs automation remain unstable given the political state of the nation.

Furthermore, low public sector pay discourage qualified IT professionals from collaborating with organisations like MPA, so contributing to a technical human resource shortage. Furthermore restricting possibilities to bring in private knowledge and money for technological developments is Myanmar's lack of clear public–private cooperation (PPP) structures.

2.4.3. Infrastructure deficits

Myanmar's poor transportation infrastructure makes port operations even more difficult. Coordination of logistics is ineffective in many ports because they are not completely connected with rail and road networks. In addition to slowing down the flow of goods, poor connectivity makes it more difficult to deploy intelligent logistics solutions like digital customs clearance, automated scheduling, and real-time cargo tracking. This significantly restricts the adoption of cutting-edge technologies that rely on integrated transportation networks by organisations such as the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA). This lack of multimodal connectivity is one of the main obstacles to port modernization and digital transformation, according to ADB's transport sector assessments (2018, 2022)⁴⁹.

2.4.4. Social factors (S)

Socially, Myanmar has serious problems with digital literacy, especially among government and mid-level port workers. The majority have received training in manual, paper-based processes, and many are ill-equipped or unwilling to switch to digital workflows. As a result, new technologies are not well received internally, which causes resistance and underuse of existing systems^{50 51}.

Additionally, there is a cultural resistance to change, as innovation is discouraged by risk-averse attitudes and traditional hierarchies. Additionally, there is little demand or pressure from citizens

⁴⁹ ADB, 2012. *Myanmar: Transport Sector Initial Assessment*. Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/institutional-document/33698/files/myanmar-transport-assessment.pdf> [Accessed 21 May 2025] (Compare to) ADB, 2016. *Myanmar Transport Sector Policy Note*. Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/184794/mya-transport-policy-note-es.pdf> [Accessed 21 May 2025].

⁵⁰ IREX, 2017. *Ending the Gender Digital Divide in Myanmar*. [online] Available at: <https://www.irex.org/sites/default/files/node/resource/overview-gender-digital-divide-myanmar-assessment.pdf> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

⁵¹ SciSpace, n.d. *A Digital Literacy Case Study in Myanmar*. [online] Available at: <https://scispace.com/pdf/a-psychosocial-analysis-of-development-outcomes-a-digital-2iq1wgbcoq.pdf> [Accessed 21 May 2025].

or port users for the government to modernise services because of low public awareness and trust in digital systems, caused by previous problems with transparency and data misuse⁵².

2.4.5. Distance in Technological Development

The Myanmar Port Authority uses mainly antiquated or manual technological systems. Customs clearance, cargo tracking, and scheduling are just a few of the processes that are still carried out with paper or Excel-based tools. Automated gates, Internet of Things-based traffic monitoring, and Port Community Systems (PCS) are examples of modern port technologies that are either nonexistent or inadequately implemented.

ICT infrastructure is also lacking in Myanmar, especially outside of major cities and Yangon. Reliable internet connections, modern hardware, and the technical assistance needed to maintain new systems are lacking in many ports. This presents a significant obstacle to scaling or integrating systems nationally in addition to restricting what can be deployed.

2.4.6. Environmental factors (E)

Although digital environmental management tools like real-time air and water quality monitoring, smart waste tracking, or emissions controls are not yet commonly used in Myanmar, the environmental aspect is becoming more and more important to contemporary port operations. Environmental audits and inspections are still typically conducted by hand, which is ineffective and irregular.

Furthermore, Myanmar's coastal infrastructure is seriously threatened by climate hazards like floods, cyclones, and sea level rise⁵³. Current MPA operations either lack or have inadequate digital tools that could help monitor and manage these risks, such as automated weather stations, early warning systems, or climate-resilient logistics planning.

2.4.7. Legal concerns (L)

Myanmar's legal system is antiquated and ill-equipped to facilitate digital transformation. For instance, the 1954 Myanmar Port Authority Law has not undergone much modernisation and does not adequately address current cybersecurity and digital issues. Lack of explicit legal provisions

⁵² Trade.gov, 2024. *Burma - Digital Economy*. [online] Available at: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/burma-digital-economy> [Accessed 1st May 2025].

⁵³ UNCTAD (2021) *Climate risk and vulnerability assessment framework for Caribbean ports*. Geneva: United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/dtltlb2021d1_en.pdf (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

for cybersecurity governance, digital procurement, or data protection erodes confidence and makes implementation more difficult⁵⁴.

Furthermore, bureaucratic red tape and uneven enforcement can impede the adoption and introduction of new technologies. Both domestic and foreign stakeholders are reluctant to contribute to or invest in digital transformation initiatives involving public institutions such as the MPA because of this regulatory uncertainty.

2.5. SWOT Analysis on MPA for the Implementation of AI

SWOT Analysis on the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) focused on the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in port operation in brief:

Strengths (Internal Positive Factors)

Myanmar's ports are positioned for future AI-driven transformation thanks to a number of fundamental strengths. Major ports like Yangon and Thilawa, which are ideally situated along important regional trade routes that link China, South Asia, and Southeast Asia, provide a solid logistical foundation for the development of AI applications in trade and maritime operations⁵⁵. The government had shown increasing interest in digital transformation before the military takeover in 2021, pursuing projects like partial automation and digitising customs procedures to update port operations⁵⁶. Furthermore, urban ports, especially Thilawa, have some basic digital systems in their current infrastructure, which makes them more suited to the gradual adoption of AI. Examples of these tools include automated scheduling and smart cargo tracking.

Weaknesses (Internal Negative Factors)

A number of significant obstacles prevent the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) from implementing AI in port operations. The organization's lack of staff trained in AI, data analytics, or even advanced ICT is one of its main limitations. This results in an excessive dependence on manual

⁵⁴ Asian Development Bank (ADB) (2020) *Myanmar: Digital Economy Development*. Manila: Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/publications/myanmar-digital-economy-development> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

⁵⁵ Asian Development Bank (ADB) (2020) *Myanmar: Digital Economy Development*. Manila: Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/publications/myanmar-digital-economy-development> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

⁵⁶ UNESCAP (2019) *Digital Transformation of Transport in Asia and the Pacific*. Bangkok: United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. Available at: <https://www.unescap.org/resources/digital-transformation-transport-asia-and-pacific> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

labour and limits the efficient operation and maintenance of AI systems⁵⁷. Furthermore, a large number of MPA's management procedures are still paper-based or only partially digitalised, and the lack of fundamental systems like Port Community Systems (PCS) makes the technical implementation of AI challenging and fragmented. Significant financial limitations further exacerbate these problems by preventing MPA from investing in AI infrastructure, hiring specialised staff, or maintaining cutting-edge technologies without outside funding or collaborations with the private sector.

Opportunities (External Positive Factors)

A number of significant obstacles prevent the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) from implementing AI in port operations. The organization's lack of staff trained in AI, data analytics, or even advanced ICT is one of its main limitations. This results in an excessive dependence on manual labour and limits the efficient operation and maintenance of AI systems.⁵⁸ Furthermore, a large number of MPA's management procedures are still paper-based or only partially digitalised, and the lack of fundamental systems like Port Community Systems (PCS) makes the technical implementation of AI challenging and fragmented⁵⁹. Significant financial limitations further exacerbate these problems by preventing MPA from investing in AI infrastructure, hiring specialised staff, or maintaining cutting-edge technologies without outside funding or collaborations with the private sector.

Threats (External Negative Factors)

The Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) is unable to integrate AI into port operations due to several major challenges. One of the organization's primary shortcomings is the absence of personnel with advanced ICT, data analytics, or AI training. This restricts the effective use and upkeep of AI systems and leads to an over-reliance on manual labour⁶⁰. Furthermore, the technical

⁵⁷ UNCTAD (2021) *Review of Maritime Transport 2021*. Geneva: United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2021_en.pdf (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

⁵⁸ UNESCAP (2019) *Digital Transformation of Transport in Asia and the Pacific*. Bangkok: United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. Available at: https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/Transport_Digital_Transformation_Report_ESCAP_2019.pdf (Accessed: 20 February 2023).

⁵⁹ Asian Development Bank (ADB) (2020) *Myanmar: Digital Economy Development*. Manila: Asian Development Bank. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/635716/myanmar-digital-economy-development.pdf> (Accessed: 20 February 2023).

⁶⁰ International Crisis Group (ICG) (2021) *Responding to the Myanmar Coup*. Available at:

implementation of AI is difficult and dispersed due to the lack of basic systems like Port Community Systems (PCS) and the fact that many MPA management procedures are still paper-based or only partially digitalised.⁶¹ These issues are further compounded by significant financial constraints that prohibit MPA from investing in AI infrastructure, employing specialised personnel, or maintaining state-of-the-art technologies without outside funding or partnerships with the private sector.

2.6. Human Resource & Organizational Resistance to Change

Alongside infrastructure and policy support, the human element is crucial for the successful adoption of technological innovation in public institutions. Resistance to change has become a significant obstacle to digital transformation in Myanmar, where the public sector is historically bureaucratic and hierarchical, especially in vital areas like port governance.

<https://www.crisisgroup.org/asia/south-east-asia/myanmar/314-responding-myanmar-coup> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

⁶¹ World Bank (2021) *Cybersecurity and Cybercrime in Developing Countries*. Washington, DC: World Bank. Available at:

<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/090224b08c2d1379/> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Figure 5: ADKAR Model in implementing change

Figure 5 the triangle format reflects the **building-block nature** of the ADKAR model:

- **Basis: Awareness and Desire** → These serve as the cornerstones of any transformation. Progress will stall if people don't understand why change is necessary and don't want it.
- **Middle Layer: Knowledge & Ability** → This is the fundamental operational stage, where employees need to be properly trained and provided with the necessary resources.
- **Top: Reinforcement** → Following implementation, changes need to be acknowledged, supported, and followed up on.

2.6.1. Application to Myanmar Port Digitalization and its challenges in HR

The ADKAR model, which identifies five essential components such as Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement which is a useful tool for comprehending organisational resistance to digital transformation in Myanmar's port industry. The advantages of smart ports and digital tools are not well understood by many public sector workers, which hinders their comprehension of the necessity of change⁶². Because they may fear losing their jobs or believe there aren't enough incentives to support the shift, employees who are unaware of new technologies are frequently less inclined to adopt them⁶³. These problems are made worse by training programs that are usually out-of-date or inconsistent, which leaves employees unprepared and ignorant of how to properly use digital solutions. Even with training, employees' capacity to apply newly acquired skills is hampered by the lack of easily accessible and user-friendly digital systems. It is also difficult to maintain change over time because institutional follow-up mechanisms are inadequate and make little attempt to normalise and reinforce digital practices.

HR Issues: Salary, Training, and the Civil Disobedience Movement

Resistance is further exacerbated by broader human resource issues. Initiative and skill development are discouraged by low public sector salaries, few opportunities for advancement, and a lack of performance incentives. Furthermore, when training programs do exist, they are frequently out-of-date, inconsistent, or unavailable to many employees. When the Civil Disobedience Movement (CDM) forced many seasoned public employees to flee or demonstrate against the government following the military coup in 2021, the situation deteriorated⁶⁴. This resulted in a lack of institutional memory, technical know-how, and project continuity, especially in intricate fields like customs automation and port modernisation⁶⁵.

⁶² Prosci (2024) *ADKAR: A model for change management*. Available at: <https://www.prosci.com/methodology/adkar> (Accessed: 21 April 2025).

⁶³ Whatfix (2023) *ADKAR model: What is it and how to use it?*. Available at: <https://whatfix.com/blog/adkar-model-what-is-it-and-how-to-use-it> (Accessed: 21 April 2025).

⁶⁴ Al Jazeera. (2023). *Myanmar's striking civil servants: Displaced, forgotten, but holding on*. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2023/8/29/myanmars-striking-civil-servants-displaced-forgotten-but-holding-on> (Accessed: 1st April 2025)

⁶⁵ Fulcrum.sg. (2025). *Myanmar's Worsening Human Resource Crisis*. Available at: <https://fulcrum.sg/myanmars-worsening-human-resource-crisis/> (Accessed: 1st April 2025).

2.7. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study is grounded in the premise that technological advancement—particularly the adoption of digital tools such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Port Community Systems (PCS), and automation which can significantly enhance the efficiency, transparency, and sustainability of public administration in the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA). The conceptual framework involves both external and internal factors that affect a historically resource-constrained and bureaucratic public institution's adoption and execution of digital transformation. This framework uses two main theoretical lenses—the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework and the ADKAR model of organisational change—to fully capture the complexity of the problem. These are used to examine the combined effects of external environmental factors and internal organisational readiness on MPA's digital transformation process.

2.7.1 Internal Factors: Organizational Change Dynamics (ADKAR Model)

Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement are the five sequential components necessary for successful organisational change, and Prosci's (2024) ADKAR model examines the Myanmar Port Authority's internal capacity to adopt technological reforms. The following is a description of each component:

- Employee and stakeholder awareness of the need for modernisation and change in port administration is measured by awareness, while departmental and individual motivation to support and participate in technological initiatives is measured by desire.
- Technical expertise and comprehension of emerging digital systems, such as AI applications, e-governance platforms, and automated cargo handling tools, are referred to as knowledge.
- Ability is a representation of MPA's operational and practical ability to successfully apply and make use of technological tools.
- Reinforcement refers to the systems established to maintain the modifications, such as incentives, performance evaluation, and institutional policies. These internal elements are influenced by human resource constraints such as low civil service salaries, lack of professional development opportunities, inadequate training programs, and the loss of experienced personnel following the 2021 Civil Disobedience Movement (CDM).

2.7.2. External Factors: Technological, Political, and Institutional Contexts (TOE Framework)

The Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework conceptualises several external factors that impact MPA's adoption of digital technology in addition to internal dynamics. These elements include:

- Organisational elements, such as bureaucratic inflexibility, antiquated governance frameworks, and poor interagency coordination;
- Technological elements, such as the accessibility and cost of ICT infrastructure, software platforms, and AI-enabled systems pertinent to port logistics.
- Environmental factors include weak legal frameworks for digital governance, political instability after the military coup in 2021, a lack of international funding, and mounting pressure to conform to international port standards.

These elements influence one another and the MPA's capacity to fund and maintain initiatives for digital transformation. For example, although international donor organisations like the World Bank and ADB encourage digital modernisation, their influence is frequently limited.

2.7.3 Integration and Expected Outcomes

According to the framework, internal readiness (as modelled by ADKAR) and the larger institutional and technological environment (as informed by TOE) must be in harmony for Myanmar's port administration to successfully undergo digital transformation. The following results are anticipated when these factors are handled comprehensively:

- **Operational Efficiency:** By combining automation and AI, improved cargo handling, shorter turnaround times, and quicker customs clearance are achieved.
- **Transparency and Governance:** Using digital record-keeping and monitoring systems can reduce corruption and enhance decision-making.
- **Economic Competitiveness:** Enhanced appeal to regional trading partners and foreign investors as a result of updated digital systems and infrastructure.
- **Sustainability:** By utilising smart port technologies that are in line with international environmental standards, environmental monitoring and regulatory compliance are enhanced.

The diagram 6, below, provides a summary of the conceptual framework and shows how internal and external factors interact to produce the anticipated results of digital transformation.

Figure 6: Text-Based Diagram for the Conceptual Framework

2.7.4 Theoretical Support

This conceptual framework offers a comprehensive understanding of the processes and obstacles associated with integrating technology into Myanmar's public sector port governance. Additionally, it provides a theoretical and analytical foundation for evaluating the data gathered in the study's later chapters.

Chapter 3: Methodology of the Research

3.1 Research Design

To methodically investigate the connection between public administration performance and technological advancement within the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA), this study employs a quantitative research design. A quantitative approach is appropriate for this study since it makes it possible to gather organised, quantifiable, and statistically analyse data in order to find trends, patterns, and connections between the variables influencing the use of contemporary technologies in port operations.⁶⁶

Descriptive-correlational in nature, the study intends to:

- Describe the MPA's current state of technological adoption, administrative effectiveness, and employee readiness;
- Examine the connections among important elements like infrastructure readiness, training accessibility, institutional support, and change resistance; and
- Determine the perceived influence of digital technologies on port performance and governance transparency.

A representative sample of MPA employees, including those from the operations, administration, engineering, and customs departments, will be given a structured survey questionnaire to collect data. The survey instrument will measure attitudes, awareness, and experience regarding technological change using closed-ended formats, multiple-choice questions, and Likert-scale items⁶⁷.

Inferential statistics, such as regression analysis or correlation analysis, will be used to test relationships between variables, while descriptive statistics, such as mean, percentage, and standard deviation, will be used to summarise respondent characteristics⁶⁸.

⁶⁶ Creswell, J.W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

⁶⁷ Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education.

⁶⁸ Babbie, E. (2013). *The Practice of Social Research*. 13th ed. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage Learning. (compare to) Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach*. 7th ed. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.

This quantitative approach is suitable for producing empirical proof that can back up data-driven suggestions for enhancing MPA's digital transformation projects⁶⁹. Additionally, it offers a methodical foundation for contrasting the results with international standards and previous research on the incorporation of technology in public sector institutions.

3.1.1. Summarize the table for this research design

Element	Detail
Study Type	Descriptive and correlational
Approaching	Quantitative
Collection type	Survey Questionnaire
Respondants	Staffs and official of MPA
Technique of analysis	Descriptive stats, correlation/regression

Table 1: Research design table

⁶⁹ **Babbie, E.R.**, 2020. *The Practice of Social Research*. 15th ed. Boston: Cengage Learning.

3.2. Data Collection and Sources

A structured survey questionnaire is used as the main instrument for quantitative data collection in this study in order to answer the research questions and objectives. The purpose of the data collection process is to obtain quantifiable information about the attitudes, preparedness, and difficulties faced by Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) staff members regarding administrative reform and technological advancement.

3.2.1 Primary Data Collection

Selected MPA employees from a variety of departments, including operations, administration, customs, engineering, and IT, were given self-administered questionnaires to complete to gather primary data. The questionnaire is primarily composed of closed-ended questions with a five-point Likert scale (from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree") to measure opinions about:

- Infrastructure and technological readiness;
- Staff competency and training;
- Administrative effectiveness;
- Opposition to technological change;
- Perceived influence of digital tools (e.g., automation, artificial intelligence);

The questionnaire is divided into sections that correspond to the conceptual framework and important variables of the study. It is possible to quantitatively analyse attitudes, trends, and correlations between institutional and technological variables by using Likert-scale items.⁷⁰

3.2.2 Secondary Data Sources

In addition to primary data, the study incorporates **secondary data** to provide contextual and comparative insights. These include:

- Official reports and publications from the Myanmar Port Authority
- Government documents and regulatory frameworks (e.g., Myanmar Port Authority Law, 1954)
- Academic literature on e-governance, AI adoption, and public sector reform

⁷⁰ Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education.

- International benchmarking reports from the Asian Development Bank (ADB), United Nations ESCAP, and the World Bank

- News articles and sectoral reviews regarding Myanmar’s technological and political developments post-2021.

These secondary sources support the interpretation of survey results and enable triangulation of data to increase research credibility.

3.2.3 Data Collection Procedures

The questionnaire was distributed in both printed and digital formats, depending on the availability and preference of respondents. However, regarding with the time and place distance, respondents are only able to answer via digital format. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity was assured to encourage honest responses. Ethical considerations such as informed consent, data privacy, and confidentiality were strictly observed throughout the data collection process.

Respondents had enough time to finish the survey during the roughly three-week data collection period. Google Forms was used to distribute the survey digitally, allowing for effective response collection, organisation, and real-time tracking. After finishing, the data was exported for analysis to Microsoft Excel and Google Sheets. To interpret the data in accordance with the goals of the study, simple descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores were employed. Since the goal of the analysis was to find trends and patterns in the responses, no sophisticated statistical software was used.

3.3 Data Analysis Methods

The analysis of the collected data in this study is primarily descriptive in nature, focusing on summarizing and interpreting quantitative responses to understand patterns, trends, and general attitudes among staff of the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) regarding technological advancement in public administration.

The responses obtained via Google Forms were automatically compiled and organized into Google Sheets, from which they were exported into Microsoft Excel for further processing. The following analysis methods were used:

- Frequency and Percentage Analysis: To describe the distribution of responses for each survey item and determine the prevalence of certain opinions or conditions (e.g., percentage of staff aware of digital tools).

- Measures of Central Tendency (Mean Scores): To assess average levels of agreement or perception on Likert-scale items, providing insights into employee attitudes towards digital transformation, infrastructure, governance, and training.
- Cross-tabulation: In selected cases, cross-tabulations were used to compare responses between different departments or demographic groups (e.g., comparing responses between operational staff and administrative staff).

Given the scope of the study and the limited use of statistical tools, inferential statistical tests such as regression or correlation analysis were not applied. The analysis focused instead on observing general patterns in the data to support conclusions and recommendations related to the research objectives.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

Ethical integrity was maintained throughout all stages of the research process to ensure the protection of participants and the credibility of the findings. The study followed standard academic ethical guidelines as outlined below:

3.4.1 Informed Consent

The goal of the study, their part in it, and their rights as respondents were all explained in detail to the participants. They were asked to electronically sign a Google Form indicating their informed consent prior to filling out the questionnaire. The consent statement made it clear that participation was completely voluntary and that there would be no repercussions if participants decided to stop at any time.

3.4.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality

The survey did not gather any personally identifiable information. Respondents received guarantees that all information would be kept completely private and used only for scholarly research. Only the researcher had access to the password-protected digital format in which the data was stored.

3.4.3 Voluntary Participation

It was completely voluntary to participate in the study. No pressure or coercion was used, and there were no rewards for taking part. Any question that respondents felt uncomfortable answering could be skipped.

3.4.4 Data Security

Every piece of information gathered using Google Forms was kept on safe, encrypted cloud servers and routinely backed up. To protect privacy and adhere to ethical research standards, the data will be kept after analysis for a brief period before being erased at the end of the study. The study made sure to respect each participant's rights, dignity, and general well-being by following these ethical guidelines.

Chapter 4: Myanma Port Authority – Myanmar Case study

4.1. Overview of Myanmar Port Authority

The Ministry of Transport and Communications manages the Myanma Port Authority (MPA), which is in charge of overseeing, controlling, and expanding Myanmar's seaports. The MPA was created by the Myanmar Port Authority Act of 1954 and is essential to promoting both domestic and foreign trade, managing port operations, guaranteeing maritime safety, and upholding environmental and shipping regulations.

Figure7: Old photo of Myanma Port Authority (former Port commissioner building)⁷¹

MPA is responsible for the operation and regulation of major ports across Myanmar, including the Port of Yangon, Thilawa Special Economic Zone Port, Sittwe Port, and several inland and regional ports. As of the latest organizational structure, the MPA comprises several specialized

⁷¹ Myanmar Port Authority (n.d.) *About*. Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/about/> (Accessed: 1May 2025)

departments, such as Marine, Traffic, Engineering, Customs Liaison, and ICT, all working together to coordinate port logistics and administration⁷².

Figure 8: Port Value of Myanmar Port Authority⁷³

With 22.4 billion dollars in value of trade, the Port of Yangon is Myanmar's most important and busiest commercial port, handling over 90% of the nation's import and export cargo volume. It has access to international shipping lanes and is ideally situated alongside the Yangon River. Situated in the Thilawa Special Economic Zone, the Thilawa Port is a cutting-edge deep-sea port and logistics centre designed to draw in foreign direct investment (FDI) and ease extensive industrial trade⁷⁴. The MPA has collaborated with several international development organisations over the years, such as the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), UNESCAP, and the Asian Development Bank (ADB), to support port infrastructure modernisation, improve environmental sustainability, and strengthen port governance through digital transformation.

The MPA still faces significant obstacles, such as antiquated technology, disjointed administrative procedures, and a lack of digital capacity, despite advancements in port infrastructure development. To enhance Myanmar's maritime competitiveness in the ASEAN region, these issues highlight the need to align MPA's operations with international standards, such as those outlined

⁷² Myanmar Port Authority. (2020). *Strategic Development Plan 2020–2030*. Ministry of Transport and Communications. Available at: <https://www.motc.gov.mm/en> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

⁷³ Myanmar Port Authority (n.d.) *About*. Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/about/> (Accessed: 1 May 2025)

⁷⁴ UNESCAP. (2022). *Digital Port Governance Toolkit*. United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. Available at: <https://www.unescap.org> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

in the Port Community System (PCS) framework and the regulations of the International Maritime Organization (IMO). In order to guarantee resilience, efficiency, and sustainability in port operations, the MPA has also released a number of strategic documents and port development plans that highlight the necessity of infrastructure investment, capacity building, and digital governance reforms.

4.2 Current Technological Practices in the Myanmar Port Authority

As the main government agency in charge of port administration, the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA) is essential to the facilitation of maritime logistics and trade. In contrast to its regional counterparts in Southeast Asia, including Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand, its adoption of contemporary technological systems is still restricted and uneven.

4.2.1 Current Digital Infrastructure

ပို့ဆောင်ရေးနှင့်ဆက်သွယ်ရေးဝန်ကြီးဌာန
မြန်မာ့ဆိပ်ကမ်းအာဏာပိုင်
အိတ်ဖွင့်တင်ဒါ(Open Tender)ခေါ်ယူခြင်း

၁။ မြန်မာ့ဆိပ်ကမ်းအာဏာပိုင်၏ ဘဏ္ဍာငွေ ရှာဖွေနိုင်မှု၊ သုံးစွဲမှု၊ ကြွေးမြီများ၊ ရရန်ရှိ/ပေးရန်ရှိ ကိစ္စရပ်များ၊ ကောက်ခံရရှိမှုများ၊ ဘဏ္ဍာရေးနှစ်အလိုက် လျာထား/သုံးစွဲမှုများကို အချိန်နှင့် တစ်ပြေး ညီဆောင်ရွက်နိုင်ရေး၊ သက်ဆိုင်ရာ ဆိပ်ကမ်းတံတားများနှင့် ကုမ္ပဏီများသို့ Bill ထုတ်ပေးရေး ကိစ္စရပ်များ၊ အရုံးအမြတ်စာရင်းများ၊ နှစ်ချုပ်လက်ကျန်ရှင်းတမ်းများအတွက် လက်ရှိဆောင်ရွက် လျက်ရှိသည့် Manual စနစ်မှ Computerized စနစ်သို့ ပြောင်းလဲဆောင်ရွက်ရန် အကောင်အထည် ဖော်ဆောင်ရွက်သွားမည်ဖြစ်ပါသည်။

၂။ အဆိုပါ စနစ်ရေးဆွဲခြင်းလုပ်ငန်းကို ဆောင်ရွက်ပေးရန်စိတ်ပါဝင်စားသည့် နည်းပညာကုမ္ပဏီများအား တင်ဒါဝင်ရောက်ယှဉ်ပြိုင်နိုင်ရန် ဖိတ်ခေါ်အပ်ပါသည်။

၃။ တင်ဒါတင်သွင်းရန်အတွက် တင်ဒါပုံစံများနှင့် စည်းမျဉ်းစည်းကမ်းချက်များကို ၃-၇-၂၀၂၄ ရက်နေ့မှ ၉-၇-၂၀၂၄ ရက်နေ့အထိ ရုံးဖွင့်ရက်များတွင် ရုံးချိန်အတွင်း မြန်မာ့ဆိပ်ကမ်းအာဏာပိုင်၊ စာရင်းဌာန တွင် လာရောက်ဝယ်ယူနိုင်ပါသည်။

၅။ တင်ဒါတင်သွင်းမှုဆိုင်ရာ သတ်မှတ်ချက်များမှာ အောက်ပါအတိုင်း ဖြစ်ပါသည်-
 (က) တင်ဒါတင်သွင်းရမည့်ရုံးလိပ်စာ - သင်တန်းခန်းမ(ပထမထပ်)၊
 ၇၆ ၀၆ ၆ ၀၆၀၀ ၆၀

Figure 9: Calling open tender to the computerized Billing Management and Budgetary Control System from the Account department⁷⁵

The organization itself tries to improve its system into computerized to catch up the globalization as its vision is to be efficient ports that ensure Myanmar seamless connection with regional and global trade and logistics chain by 2030, as shown in figure 9. Therefore, it also means that they have a deep interest in changing the system into computerized or digitalized, which can tend to use AI in the future for globalization.

Currently, MPA uses a partially digital port management system, with its main focus being on Thilawa and Yangon ports. The shift from paper-based procedures to electronic documentation and tracking systems has advanced somewhat, particularly in the areas of basic customs-related

⁷⁵ Myanmar Port Authority (2024) ‘Billing Management and Budgetary Control System Tender Announcement’, *Tenders and Announcement*, 2 July. Available at: <https://www.mpa.gov.mm/tenders-and-announcement/> (Accessed: 23 May 2025).

documentation, berthing arrangements, and vessel scheduling. Although basic ICT tools like database archiving, email-based coordination, and Excel are utilised, there is a significant lack of centralised digital integration. Most activities, including cargo handling, gate management, and customs inspection, are still done by hand at the Port of Yangon, despite restricted access to online manifest submissions and cargo tracking systems. This dependence on manual processing raises the possibility of administrative errors, delays, and inefficiencies.

4.2.2. Summary of Gaps and Limitations

In summary, MPA's current technology practices are best described as fragmented and transitional, with selective digitisation, outdated equipment, and a lack of comprehensive digital governance. Due to a lack of system-wide integration and low levels of digital literacy among its staff, the MPA is less able to take full advantage of smart port technologies, which makes it less competitive in the global logistics market. To remain competitive on a regional and global level, the MPA must create a fully integrated digital infrastructure that includes single-window systems, automated scheduling, real-time cargo tracking, and robust digital governance regulations.

4.3. Stakeholder Insights

The viewpoints of internal stakeholders, particularly the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA), are crucial for understanding the elements that support and impede successful digital transformation in the fields of technology and public administration. In addition to reflecting current practices, stakeholder insights demonstrate organisational readiness, resistance, and change capacity. The views and experiences of MPA's staff are essential to the success of any modernisation project because it is a large, multi-departmental organisation responsible for managing the country's major trade ports. Because they actively manage logistics, implement port policies, and engage with both local and international stakeholders, these stakeholders have a unique perspective on the institutional realities of port governance in Myanmar.

4.4. Myanmar Port Authority Law (1954): Historical Context, Legal Framework, and Comparative Perspective

The **Myanmar Port Authority Law of 1954** is a pivotal legislative instrument that established the **Myanmar Port Authority (MPA)** as the central body responsible for the administration, regulation, and development of port infrastructure across Myanmar. Promulgated during the early post-independence period, the law reflects the government's strategic intent to assert national control over critical maritime gateways, which were essential for economic reconstruction and international trade following colonial rule.⁷⁶

Historical Context

⁷⁶ Aye Chan, *The Port Acts of Burma: 1905–1962* (Yangon: University of Yangon Press, 1980), 45.

After Myanmar gained independence in 1948, there was an urgent necessity to assert sovereign authority over essential economic sectors, especially transportation and commerce. Ports, having been established and managed primarily under colonial rule, necessitated a structured shift to national authority. Squared The implementation of the Myanmar Port Authority Law in 1954 represented a pivotal development, establishing a legal foundation for the nationalisation of port management, the advancement of marine commerce, and the incorporation of port operations into the comprehensive economic planning of the newly independent state. Legal Provisions and **Institutional Framework**

The legislation designates the Myanmar Port Authority as a legal entity endowed with extensive powers and obligations. Key provisions encompass

- **Organizational Formation:** Establishment of an administrative entity empowered to supervise port activities, assign staff, and enter into contracts pertaining to port operations. **Regulatory Authority:** The capacity to promulgate enforceable port regulations, oversee vessel navigation, administer berthing operations, and supervise cargo management to guarantee efficiency and safety.
- **Revenue Collection:** Legal authority to levy port dues, wharfage fees, storage costs, and other associated tariffs is essential for the financial viability of port services.
- **Infrastructure Development:** Authorization to construct, maintain, and enhance port infrastructure, encompassing docks, warehouses, and navigational aids.
- **Safety and Security Enforcement:** Measures to preserve maritime safety, safeguard port assets, and uphold environmental protections⁷⁷.

⁷⁷ Ministry of Transport & Communications, *Myanmar Ports and Shipping Regulations* (Yangon: Ministry of Transport, 2006), 23–33.

The legal framework prioritizes centralized governance, operational efficacy, and public accountability, which are crucial for overseeing Myanmar's vital maritime resources⁷⁸.

Comparative Analysis

In comparison to port authority legislation in other nations, such as Singapore's Port Authorities Act (1963) or Malaysia's Harbours Act (1952), the Myanmar Port Authority Law exhibits similar features in creating centralised control and regulatory monitoring.⁴ Nevertheless, although port regulations in more advanced maritime countries have progressed to include liberalisation, public-private partnerships, and contemporary environmental standards, the Myanmar Port Authority Law of 1954 maintains a more conventional, state-focused framework that mirrors its post-independence circumstances⁷⁹.

In contrast to the Singaporean model, which has evolved into a corporatised framework prioritizing efficiency and global competitiveness, the Myanmar model, established by the 1954 law, continues to adhere closely to public sector administration, exhibiting minimal structural reforms in the ensuing decades.⁴ This comparison underscores the potential for legislative modernisation to enhance Myanmar's port governance in accordance with international best practices.

The Myanmar Port entity Law (1954) established a centralised entity for the regulation, management, and development of port facilities in Myanmar. This law is moulded by its historical setting and continues to impact the operational and strategic framework of Myanmar's maritime sector. Nevertheless, when assessed against worldwide benchmarks, the law reveals opportunities for revision to improve efficiency, encourage investment, and assure conformity with modern global norms in port administration.

⁷⁸ Capt. Ye Naing, *Evolution of International Port State Regime, and Myanmar Port State Jurisdiction and Control* (Yangon: Myanmar Maritime University, 2019), 12–55.

⁷⁹ John Roger, *Maritime Law and Governance in Southeast Asia* (London: Routledge, 2005), 112–117.

4.4.1 Planned Survey Objectives and Scope

A wide range of attitudes, experiences, and expectations regarding digital practices at MPA are meant to be captured by the structured questionnaire used in this study. 50 Employees from various departments will receive the survey, including:

- Logistics and operations;
- Administrative and policy departments;
- Safety and marine engineering;
- ICT and infrastructure groups;
- Documentation and customs liaison

The survey's primary goals are to:

- Evaluate how digital technologies are currently used in MPA operations;
- Recognise institutional barriers to adopting new technologies;
- Gauge staff attitudes towards digital change and modernisation;
- Gain insight into staff perceptions of organisational capacity and digital readiness; and
- Gather useful recommendations for enhancing technological integration.

4.4.2 Key Thematic Areas

To guarantee a systematic examination of stakeholder perspectives, the questionnaire will be separated into thematic sections:

A. Digital Usage and Infrastructure

This section will investigate how frequently and how employees use digital tools in their day-to-day work. It will look at the availability and functionality of systems like digital documentation, scheduling platforms, and cargo tracking. Additionally, it will look for areas where manual processes are still prevalent and why.

B. Education, Proficiency, and Digital Knowledge

This theme focuses on human resource development, evaluating whether staff members feel confident in their digital skills and have received sufficient training to use the available systems. Additionally, it will investigate whether training opportunities are current, relevant, and easily accessible.

C. Leadership Commitment and Institutional Support

Stakeholders will be asked to score how supportive they believe their organisations are of digital transformation. This includes leadership vision, departmental cooperation, budgeting for technology, and responsiveness to staff feedback. Finding misalignments will require an understanding of how top-down policies are viewed at the local level.

D. Perceptions of Resistance and Change

This section will concentrate on psychological and cultural preparedness for digital transformation, acknowledging that resistance to change is a prevalent obstacle in public sector modernization. Questions will focus on openness to change, perceived job security, trust in new systems, and employee motivation.

E. Governance, Regulation, and Policy

Participants will be asked to share their thoughts on how the regulatory environment either encourages or inhibits innovation. This includes opinions about the flexibility, clarity, and

enforcement of laws and procedures about ports, like the Myanmar Port Authority Law of 1954, which many stakeholders feel needs immediate reform.

F. Recommendations and Prospective Perspectives

Additionally, suggestions for enhancements will be welcomed from the respondents. These could be system improvements, leadership changes, policy adjustments, or improved cooperation with foreign development partners.

4.4.3 Value of Stakeholder Insights Expected

Stakeholder responses will provide a solid understanding of MPA's internal strengths, weaknesses, and preparedness to embrace contemporary technologies once they have been gathered and examined. These revelations will help with:

Policy suggestions based on staff realities as opposed to high-level presumptions
Route maps for system upgrades that take user preferences and operational limitations into account.

Training and capacity-building tactics that are adapted to real needs; and

Improved alignment between institutional culture and strategic vision

Chapter 5: Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

5. Summary of Findings

The findings from the MPA Digital Transformation Staff Questionnaire provide a snapshot of the organization's current state of digital transformation, as perceived by its employees. These findings represent the existing degree of preparation, ongoing obstacles, and attitudes towards modernizing port operations. The responses, gathered from various departments and functions, are summarized into seven main areas:

Application of Digital Tools and Systems

Staff workflows are moderately digitally integrated. While many employees report using computerized systems daily, manual procedures are still frequent, especially in departments where full digitization has not been achieved. The mix of manual and digital technologies implies that MPA is still making a gradual digital shift.

Perceptions about digital infrastructure

Staff consider MPA's digital infrastructure adequate but not remarkable. When compared to global port standards, the infrastructure is regarded as lacking in various areas. This could indicate difficulties such as old technology, sluggish acceptance of new systems, or insufficient investment in IT resources.

Training and Digital Competence

Training is a major concern. While some employees are well-prepared and competent in using digital tools, many others lament a lack of proper training. This inequality is likely to lead to varied levels of digital literacy and operational effectiveness throughout the organisation.

Regulatory and legal challenges.

A sizable proportion of respondents felt that the Myanmar Port Authority Law (1954) is out of date and hinders the scope for genuine digital reform. There is substantial support for connecting the MPA's digital strategy with worldwide regulatory norms to secure global competitiveness and legal strength.

Feedback and Engagement from Staff

Inclusionary participation in the digital decision-making process is lacking, according to the survey. Many employees believe that when digital technologies are being implemented, their input is not actively sought out or taken into account. This impression might reduce support and reduce the efficacy of digital projects.

Data privacy and cybersecurity

Employees are becoming more conscious of the significance of data protection and cybersecurity. As more systems move to digital platforms, many employees think that the lack of official cybersecurity standards is a serious weakness.

Employee Representation

Responses to the survey came from a variety of departments, mostly Engineering and Administration, and positions, such as office workers, mechanical staff, and executive engineers. Additionally, respondents' ages and lengths of service varied, guaranteeing a representative and well-rounded dataset.

Average Rating across Key Questions

Figure 10: Average Rating across key questions

According to Figure 10, the interesting average staff ratings for each of the major aspects of MPA's digital transformation experience are displayed in the chart. Interestingly, the second highest score indicates a high level of confidence in the use of digital technologies, indicating that employees are typically at ease with technology in their jobs. In addition to this, some of the employees recruited by MPA were either new or young recent graduates, which is unconditionally accustomed to technological skills and knowledge of tech tools applications.

Moreover, assumingly that most employees are staying in Yangon, the biggest commercial city, who at least own mobile phones and laptops, can access knowledge of advanced technological and other influential workplaces, especially compared to private workplaces in Yangon. Therefore, according to the statistics surveys, the employees are eager to change and transform into an advanced technological workplace in order to be released from multi-tasking, workload pressure, and full loads of paperwork with the old and consuming unnecessary space to put those.

The appropriateness of training, on the other hand, receives a 3.49 rating, suggesting a serious lack of assistance and skill development. As complicated political, economic, and budgetary conflicts, these two components may remain distant unless the armaments budget is reduced. This emphasises the urgent need for more focused, organised digital training programs to guarantee that employees are not only competent but also ready to use technology efficiently.

The lowest-rated item was “MPA’s digital infrastructure is comparable to that of other ports in Southeast Asia”, with an average score of 3.04. This suggests that staff perceive MPA’s infrastructure as lagging behind regional peers, pointing to a need for significant investment in modernization and benchmarking. On the other end, the highest-rated item was “Manual procedures are still dominant in my department”, with an average score of 3.92. While this might appear positive at first glance, the statement itself is negatively framed — a higher score indicates a greater reliance on manual work, which is counterproductive to digital transformation goals. This underscores the urgency of accelerating process automation and reducing paper-based or manual systems.

The Myanmar Port Authority's organisational preparedness for digital transformation and individual digital confidence differ significantly, according to the staff survey results. Even though most respondents believe they can use digital tools, there is a strong belief that MPA's digital infrastructure falls short of regional norms. In addition, the persistent dependence on manual

procedures and doubts about the quality of training highlight systemic issues that could impede advancement. Modernising infrastructure, cutting down on manual workflows, and bolstering staff training and support systems should be the main strategic priorities in order to facilitate a successful and long-lasting change.

5.1. Discussion of the Results

A thorough examination of the staff members' answers to the Myanmar Port Authority's (MPA) digital transformation survey is given in the part that follows. Interpreting the quantitative input obtained in several important theme areas—such as the use of digital tools, the sufficiency of the infrastructure, training and assistance, manual processes, and regulatory preparedness—is the main goal. This conversation seeks to pinpoint positives, highlight significant obstacles, and place staff perceptions within MPA's larger digital transformation initiatives by looking at average ratings and response trends. The knowledge gained here will help guide evidence-based suggestions for a future implementation approach that is more cogent and successful. The questionnaire is divided into five sessions, and here are the results below-

5.1.1. Section I: Digital Infrastructure and Usage

This section includes the internal assessment of MPA's employees' current digital usage and its infrastructure situation which includes as shown below--

Digital tools and systems adequacy in daily work

For my everyday work, MPA's digital tools and systems are adequate.

50 responses

Figure 11: Bar Graph showing MPA Employees's assessment of digital tools and systems adequacy

Figure 11 shows the survey results regarding the adequacy of digital tools and systems used in their daily work. According to the data, nearly 38% agree with the positive aspects related to tools and systems, while 32% stay neutral on the Likert scale. This expresses that around 70% of the employees are pleased with the infrastructure, which is reasonably adequate. Nevertheless, 18% chose to express dissatisfaction, and only 4% rated strongly disagree. These results outlined that while the infrastructure is generally sufficient, there remain things for improvement to increase employees' satisfaction.

The perception of the staff of the usage computerized system in the operational port

Computerised systems are used in our port to track cargo and process customs clearance.

50 responses

Figure 12: Bar Graph showing perception of the staff regarding computerized system usage in Port operation

The bar graph above displays the answered regarding the use of computerized systems for tracking cargo and the customs clearance process at the port. Surprisingly, half of the respondents chose that most employees know how the use the system effectively and are currently using it. The neutral and negative views with 20%, 6 %, and 8% percentage respectively. To conclude this, the results clearly show a confidence level of positive agreement on the case of actively using computerised systems in their operations.

Daily tasks usage of digital tools how frequency

In my work, I frequently use digital tools or systems (e.g., port scheduling, cargo logs, emails).
50 responses

Figure 13: Bar Graph of the frequent use of digital tools or systems in daily work by employees

Figure 13, describes how frequently digital tools or systems are used in their daily tasks by the employees for things like cargo tracking, scheduling the port, or sending emails. With over 50% of the employees choosing agreed and 12 % choosing strongly agreed means frequent digital attachment. However, there are still 8% and 2% selected disagreed and strongly disagreed factors, and 20% chose to stay neutral, which means some areas of the workplace do not use much of digital tools. Lastly, to conclude with this, the above explanation shows that most employees' daily responsibilities are part of integral to the digital tools.

Domination of manual procedures in Departments

Manual procedures are still dominant in my department.

50 responses

Figure 14: Bar Graph of the respondents ' dominance of manual Procedures in departments

Although employees frequently use digital tools or systems in their daily tasks Figure 13, these results stated that a significant portion of employees agree with the domination of manual procedures in their respective departments in figure 14, with 44% and 28% rated with strongly agree. A small minority, with a total of 6%, rated as strongly disagree with this statement. Therefore, according to the results, it is true that manual procedures are still dominant in departments that slow the pathway of transformation to digital practically.

Comparison between Southeast Asian ports to MPA regarding digital infrastructure

MPA's digital infrastructure is comparable to that of other ports in Southeast Asia.

50 responses

Figure 15: Bar Graph of comparison with Southeast Asian ports to MPA regarding digital infrastructure by the respondents

The results show the surprising fact that the most frequent response with nearly 40% expressing neutral or mixed opinions, or scared. 28% and 4% of respondents chose to disagree with this, which indicates employees feel below or just average to the digital infrastructure compared to regional countries. However, there is still a chance to make improvements to meet the regional standards.

5.1.2. Section II: Training, Knowledge & Skills (ADKAR – Knowledge, Ability)

This part looks at how workers feel about the training, knowledge, and skills they have acquired to help with digital transformation. It focuses on the Knowledge and Ability parts of the ADKAR model.

Sufficient need for training is given to use digital systems

I have received adequate training to operate the digital systems provided.

50 responses

Figure 16: Respondents' results Bar Graph of sufficient training is given to apply digital systems

Figure 16 shows that 44% of employees received training, but not fully, and only 10% gave a strong agreement rate, showing they were well-trained with the digital systems. Nevertheless, only 14% of the total disagree with the statement, which is interesting that the organization put effort into training aspects. While most employees received some training on digital systems, further advanced development, training infrastructure, and continuous support are still needed to ensure complete readiness.

Confidence in the job to use digital platforms

I feel confident in using digital platforms related to my role.

50 responses

Figure 17: Confidence in the job to use digital platforms bar graph

Over 50 % of employees selected with the agreement which shows a high level of confidence, and even 20% gave a strongly agree rate, while only 8% of the total still face some challenges in using the digital platforms related to their role. In general the level of confidence is higher than expected, while there is a notable group that needs more training and support.

Updated and relevant training provided by MPA’s training programs

Training provided by MPA is up-to-date and relevant to the systems we use.

50 responses

Figure 18: Updated and relevant training provided by MPA’s training programs, Bar graph

Many respondents agree with this statement positively, with 42% and 20% with 4 and 5. While 28% stay in neutral, which means moderately satisfied with the training, there are a few groups that gave a 10% rating with a low rating in Figure 18. Accordingly, most of the employees believed that the training provided by MPA is current and relevant to their system they apply. However, there is still a process to improve relevance and customization to the workplace and AI training.

The availability of technical support for the digital system when issues arise

When technical issues come up, there is continuous support available.

50 responses

Figure 19: Bar Graph of respondents to Immediate technical support for the digital system when issues arise

In this bar graph, 32% of the respondents show a moderate agreement with this statement, while 22% rated as 2, which means there is a gap in consistent support. Interestingly, 14% of the employees show strong approval as they get full support, but only a few among them do. It illustrated that the support does, but it needs to improve consistent and fast response, mainly to the people who are lower-rated users.

Specialized digital training for overall efficiency

I believe more specialized digital training would improve overall efficiency.

50 responses

Figure 20: Bar Graph of respondents' results of demand for specialized digital training

44% and 36% strongly agree that more specialized training is needed to improve overall port efficiency, while only a small portion, 2-10 %, disagree. Therefore, employees would like to have more targeted and sophisticated digital training as the current provided training seems generalized or insufficient for the specific role.

5.1.3. Section III: Awareness, Desire & Resistance to Change

During this section, explain the staff survey results and talk about what they suggest so that we can better understand how the staff feels about MPA's digital transformation.

Knowing what MPA's Digital Transformation goals are

I am aware of MPA's digital transformation and modernization goals.

50 responses

Figure 21: Results of respondents, knowing what MPA's Digital Transformation goals are

According to the study results in Figure 21, just 12% of respondents are completely aware of MPA's digital transformation and modernisation aims, while a significant percentage (26%), 54%, are only moderately aware of them. This suggests that even while the business has made some strides in explaining its objectives, there is still a large knowledge gap among employees. MPA should improve its internal communication tactics, such as frequent updates, interactive briefings, and easily available documentation, to increase engagement and alignment and make sure that all staff members are aware of the direction and goal of the company's digital transformation initiatives.

Supportiveness of Digital transformation and AI development

I support the adoption of modern technologies like automation and AI at MPA.
50 responses

Figure 22: Supportiveness of the respondents' survey result for adopting technologies such as automation and AI at MPA

Staff support for implementing and adopting digital technology, like automation and artificial intelligence tools, is shown in this chart. With 44% rating 4 and 16% rating 5, the majority of respondents showed a favourable attitude, demonstrating their openness and readiness to use cutting-edge digital technologies, according to Figure 22. However, 30% are staying in the neutral, which might be related to Figure 23, fear of losing their job, and future uncertainty.

Fear of losing the current Job analysis

Some workers are reluctant to use digital systems because they fear losing their jobs.
50 responses

Figure 23: Respondents’ answers regarding replacing or losing their jobs

A more critical and nuanced view of how the staff members view the process of digital transformation is provided by the graphic 23. When asked if any employees worry about losing their jobs because of the plan to use or replace digital technology, a sizable percentage of respondents said they do. In particular, 28% strongly agreed and 30% agreed with this statement, indicating that over half of the participants—58% in total—acknowledge the existence of this anxiety inside the organisation. In contrast, 14% had no opinion, 20% disagreed, and 8% strongly disagreed, indicating that while the concern is noticeable, not everyone shares it. This conflicting reaction shows that there is a real undercurrent of fear about possible job loss even in a setting where the majority embrace digital change.

Motivation regarding technological transformation to use in the department

Figure 24: Motivation regarding technological transformation to use in the department

This graphic 24, shows a very positive trend in terms of employee enthusiasm to adjust to technology changes. In particular, a significant feeling of personal preparedness and desire to embrace digital transformation was shown by the fact that 60% of respondents evaluated their motivation at level 4, and another 24% rated it at the highest level of 5. In addition to being aware of the impending changes, this high degree of motivation indicates that the workforce is positively disposed to support and participate in the shift. Since motivated employees are more inclined to interact with new systems, take part in training, and support the organisational change as a whole, such proactive attitudes among staff members are essential to the success of digital efforts. MPA

has a great chance to further empower its employees by giving them the resources, assistance, and skills they need to maintain this momentum in light of this discovery.

Digital Innovation Is Slowed Down by Bureaucratic Culture

Bureaucratic culture in MPA slows down digital innovation.
51 responses

Figure 25: Digital innovation is slowed down by Bureaucratic culture

The bureaucratic culture at MPA is seen by many respondents as a hindrance to digital advancement, as shown in Figure 25. 22% strongly agreed and 44% agreed that digital innovation is slowed down by bureaucratic convention. The implication is that although there may be strategic goals, their implementation may be hindered by rigidity in procedures and structures. Accelerating transformation initiatives will require addressing these organisational obstacles.

5.1.4. Section IV: Institutional Support & Leadership

This section looks at how staff members see the institution's support and the leadership's function in effectively communicating and directing the process of digital transformation.

Leadership Promotes Digital Modernization

Leadership in MPA actively promotes digital modernization.
51 responses

Figure 26: Leadership Promotes Digital Modernization

The majority of respondents (74%) agreed that MPA leadership actively promotes digital modernization, with an additional 8% strongly agreeing. This indicates a positive perception of leadership's role in driving change. The high level of agreement reflects trust in leadership's vision and highlights their importance as enablers of digital transformation within the institution.

Resource Allocation for Technological Advancement

Resources and funds are set aside by my department for the advancement of technology.
51 responses

Figure 27: Resource Allocation for Technological Advancement Survey Results

In terms of financial commitment, 24% of respondents were indifferent, and 62% of respondents agreed that their departments allocate money for developing technology. In terms of funding digital projects, this indicates a moderate to high level of institutional preparedness. But according to the neutral and disagreeing segments (24% + 8%), there could still be discrepancies in how resources are distributed among departments.

Digital adoption in port operations is improved through cross-departmental coordination

Digital adoption in port operations is improved through cross-departmental coordination.

51 responses

Figure 28: Digital adoption in port operations is improved through cross-departmental coordination survey results pie chart

Among employees, a sizable majority (74%) agree or strongly agree that cross-departmental collaboration promotes digital adoption in Figure 28. This suggests that departmental cooperation is seen as a vital facilitator of digital change in port operations. There is little opposition to interdepartmental cooperation, as seen by the tiny percentage (6%) that disagree. The significance of enhancing cross-functional collaboration and communication as a component of your digital transformation plan is underscored by this study.

MPA leadership communicates the benefits of digital change clearly

MPA leadership communicates the benefits of digital change clearly.
51 responses

Figure 29: MPA leadership communicates the benefits of digital change clearly survey result pie chart

With 64% agreeing and 16% strongly agreeing, an optimistic 80% of respondents think leadership successfully conveys the value of digital change in this pie chart 29. No one strongly disagrees, and just 8% disagree. This implies that the majority of employees are successfully receiving leadership communications on digital goals. Even while the results are generally favourable, more frequent or tailored messaging, particularly emphasising how digital transformation fits with departmental objectives and individual roles, might be helpful for the 12% who feel ambivalent.

Perceived Value of Staff Feedback in Digital Implementation

I feel my feedback on digital implementation is taken seriously.

51 responses

Figure 28: Perceived Value of Staff Feedback in Digital Implementation survey results pie chart

The majority of employees believe that leadership acknowledges and takes seriously their input on digital adoption, according to poll results in Figure 28. A majority of respondents (58%), with 14% strongly agreeing, had a generally good opinion of the organization's feedback mechanisms. The fact that 8% disagreed and 20% of staff were ambivalent indicates that although most workers feel heard, there is still an opportunity to enhance the way that input is gathered, acknowledged, and used. This research highlights the need to preserve open, transparent channels of communication so employees may provide suggestions and observe how their efforts affect the decision-making process.

5.1.5. Section V: Policy, Regulation & Governance

This section explores staff perceptions of the existing policies, regulations, and governance structures, focusing on their effectiveness and readiness to support MPA’s digital transformation efforts.

Current port regulations support digital transformation effectively.

Current port regulations support digital transformation effectively.

51 responses

Figure 29:

Survey Result Pie Chart of current port regulations supporting digital transformation effectively

There appears to be a strong regulatory base since the majority of employees (66%) think that current port laws encourage digital transformation. A tiny minority (8%) disagree, while 26% are indifferent, which may indicate that there are certain parts of the regulations that need clarification or improvement.

Myanmar Port Authority Law (1954) is outdated and needs reform

Myanmar Port Authority Law (1954) is outdated and needs reform.

51 responses

Figure 30: The Myanmar Port Authority Law (1954) is outdated and needs reform

An overwhelming **80% of respondents** believe the MPA Law from 1954 is **outdated and needs reform**, indicating strong support for modernization in Figure 30. Only a small group (10%) disagrees, reinforcing the urgency and broad consensus on the need for legislative updates to match digital transformation goals.

The absence of cybersecurity and data privacy laws affects system trust.

The absence of cybersecurity and data privacy laws affects system trust.

51 responses

Figure 31: The absence of cybersecurity and data privacy laws affects system trust.

A significant majority (66.7%) agreed that the lack of cybersecurity and data privacy laws impacts trust in digital systems, with an additional 13.7% strongly agreeing. This highlights a critical

concern among staff regarding the security and reliability of digital platforms, indicating that strengthening cybersecurity regulations could improve system acceptance and trust.

Government policies provide enough incentives for digital port development.

Government policies provide enough incentives for digital port development.
51 responses

Figure 32: Government policies provide enough incentives for digital port development survey result pie chart

The majority of respondents (52.9%) agreed, with 9.8% strongly agreeing, that government policies provide adequate support for the development of digital ports. Even if the majority had a good opinion, the fact that there were neutral (19.6%) and disagreeing (15.7%) replies indicates that there could still be areas where policy clarity, communication, or perceived efficacy need to be improved.

International Standards

I believe international standards should guide MPA's digital upgrade process.
51 responses

Figure 33: International Standard

68% of respondents agree and 18% strongly agree that international standards should guide MPA's digital transformation, indicating strong support for global benchmarking in Figure 33. Leverage this positive attitude by integrating internationally recognized digital frameworks (e.g., ISO/IEC standards) in upcoming digital initiatives.

Additional Information

Demographics—Department, Years of Service, and Role

Department

Department

51 responses

Figure 34: Department

The respondents came from various departments, with the largest group (28%) working in Custom, followed by 24% from the Communication department, and 12% each from Operations, Administration, and Engineering. This shows a well-rounded participation across different operational areas, giving the survey a balanced departmental perspective.

Years of Service and Current Role

Years of Service at MPA

51 responses

Figure 35: Years of Service

Current Role
51 responses

Figure 36: Current Role

The survey participants had a diverse spectrum of work experience within MPA, ranging from almost two years to more than thirty years, as seen in Figure 35. The response is largely from mid-career professionals, as evidenced by the fact that the largest group (16%) has 15 years of experience. By contributing a blend of new ideas and extensive institutional memory, this diversity guarantees that both younger and more seasoned staff members are included in the discussion about digital transformation.

While the replies include a variety of operational and administrative responsibilities, the responses are dispersed throughout several present positions, with somewhat greater concentrations in Junior Accountant 2 (8%) and JE2 (6%) in Figure 36. This suggests that the survey was successful in gathering opinions from a variety of departments and job levels, demonstrating how the issue of digital transformation affects every level of the company.

Age Group

Age Group
51 responses

Figure 37: Age

A multigenerational workforce was surveyed; the largest age group was 55+ (34%), closely followed by 25–34 (28%) and 35–44 (28%) in Figure 37. Although there are many senior, experienced personnel, younger people are equally well-represented, as this balanced distribution shows. This combination supports cross-generational collaboration in the process of change by combining digital-native attitudes with seasoned wisdom, which is advantageous for digital transformation.

Conclusion of all the results above

The survey's findings shed important light on MPA employees' present attitudes, level of preparedness, and worries about the upcoming digital transition. The majority of employees show high levels of motivation and a strong desire to adjust to technological developments, which is indicative of a generally optimistic view in the replies. Employees usually believe that their opinions about the use of digital technology are respected, and they have a great deal of faith in the leadership's commitment to this change. But several serious issues were also noted, namely with the quality of training, how well MPA's digital infrastructure compares to global norms, and the anxiety over possible automation-related job loss.

Government incentives, policy backing, and cybersecurity concerns were also emphasised as critical elements that might affect the outcome of digital projects. The demographic distribution also shows that the workforce is heterogeneous by age group, department, and years of service, indicating that customised approaches will be necessary to meet different demands within the company. To make sure that the digital transformation is inclusive, successful, and long-lasting, it will be essential to improve training programs, solve job security issues, improve communication, and strengthen governance and regulatory frameworks going forward.

5.2. Policy and Practical Recommendation

A few crucial actions should be made in order to assist MPA in continuing its digital transition. Initially, it is critical to ensure the security of digital systems and the protection of the personal data of each and every employee. Many employees expressed their concerns about security and their belief that the safeguards in place are insufficient. Progress may be slowed down when people don't feel secure utilising new technology. To foster confidence, MPA should establish unambiguous guidelines that safeguard everyone's data and instruct employees on how to use digital technologies safely. Regular, easy training sessions may make everyone feel more prepared and confident.

Better training and assistance for employees to develop their digital abilities is another crucial step. According to the poll, even if most people are eager to learn and participate in digital developments, many still believe they don't know enough or are afraid that new technology would cause them to lose their employment. MPA ought to provide hands-on training that aligns with what employees genuinely require for their everyday jobs. Training must be simple, accessible, and provide opportunities for individuals to put what they have learnt into practice. Asking employees for their opinions regularly and demonstrating that you value their opinions are equally crucial, as mentioned in the discourse ethics. Everyone will feel more supported and participate in the process as a result.

Finally, to adapt to the contemporary digital environment, some of the existing workplace regulations and policies must be changed. The way ports and digital systems operate now is different from many of these standards, which were developed a long time ago. To further support the organization's digital objectives, MPA should evaluate and update these regulations in collaboration with government officials and employees. These adjustments can also be guided by seeing what other prosperous ports are doing globally.

In conclusion, developing secure technology, offering helpful training, and updating the regulations to accommodate new methods of operation are all critical to MPA's success as a digital organization. People are far more likely to welcome change and contribute to the success of the digital transition when they feel heard, protected, and supported.

5.3. Conclusion

This research examined the difficulties the MPA has had implementing new technology, with particular attention to institutional support, personnel preparedness, training, policy gaps, and attitudes towards digital transformation. According to the data, there are still several obstacles, even though MPA personnel are typically highly motivated and receptive to digital transformation. Concerns about job security, inadequate training, antiquated regulatory frameworks, and inadequate cybersecurity measures are some of the main obstacles. Furthermore, even if there is obvious motivation in taking part in the digital transformation, many employees believe that the implementation process does not completely take into account their input. The findings emphasise how crucial it is to create a welcoming workplace where employees receive training and actively participate in formulating policies and decisions. To properly enable this digital change, it will also be necessary to update regulations and enhance organisational communication. In the end, MPA's ability to successfully integrate technology advancements with the human elements of change, making sure that employees feel capable, protected, and appreciated throughout the process, will determine how successful its technological advancements are.

5.4. Further research direction

Even though this study offers insightful information on the difficulties MPA is now facing in its digital transformation, other topics still need more research. Future studies should look at how staff members at different levels, for instance, front-line employees vs senior management, perceive technology advancements and whether or not their experiences differ much. As digital systems are progressively implemented and enhanced, longitudinal studies may also help monitor how employee attitudes, abilities, and confidence levels change over time. A wider view of best practices and creative ideas that MPA may use might also be provided by comparison studies with other international port authorities. Examining how certain leadership styles, training initiatives, and policy revisions affect digital effectiveness might yield useful suggestions for upcoming initiatives. Future research can help develop more effective ways that support the advancement of technology and the individuals driving that change by pursuing these topics further.

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Appendix

MPA Digital Transformation Survey – Staff Questionnaire

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Informed Consent Form

Dear Participant,

You are invited to take part in a research study entitled “**Technological Advancement and Public Administration: Challenges Faced by the Myanmar Port Authority.**” This survey is part of a master’s thesis conducted at the University of Wrocław, focusing on how technological transformation impacts the operations, governance, and staff experience at the Myanmar Port Authority (MPA).

Your participation is **voluntary**, and all your responses will be kept **confidential and anonymous**. The survey is expected to take around **10–15 minutes**.

No personally identifiable information will be collected. The data will be used solely for academic purposes. By continuing, you confirm that:

- You have read and understood the purpose of this study.
- You agree to participate in the survey voluntarily.
- You understand that you may stop at any time without consequence.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact the researcher via:

✉ **Email:** 348586@uwr.edu.pl

✉ **Supervisor Email:** barbara.kowalczyk@uwr.edu.pl

Figure 38: Respondents’ consent form

Questionnaire link

<https://forms.gle/jpwwcjNQAjxYMvHw5>